

Preventing Infections in Adolescents with Gastrointestinal Disorders

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Topic: Gastrointestinal Disorders

Title: Preventing Infections in Adolescents with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Objectives: To explore how adolescents with gastrointestinal disorders can prevent secondary infections through lifestyle and medical strategies.

Background: Adolescents with gastrointestinal disorders, such as irritable bowel syndrome and inflammatory bowel disease, often experience gut microbiota imbalance, which weakens their immune system and increases the risk of secondary infections. Factors like diet, stress, and inadequate hygiene can worsen this risk. Medical strategies, including proper medication use, vaccination, and regular check-ups, combined with healthy lifestyle habits like balanced nutrition and stress management, are key to preventing infections. Exploring how lifestyle and medical strategies together can reduce infection risk is crucial to improving adolescent health outcomes.

Methods: To analyze the literature, we retrieved 348 preliminary articles by inputting the following search terms into PubMed and Web of Science Core Collection: *adolescents*, *gastrointestinal disorders*, *secondary infections*, and *preventive strategies*. We applied exclusion criteria to remove studies focused exclusively on adult populations and articles unrelated to infection prevention. Of the articles that remained we selected the 100 most cited articles and exported their bibliometric data for further analysis.

Results: After analyzing the top 100 most cited articles related to adolescents with gastrointestinal disorders, two major themes emerged. The first group of articles focused on medical strategies to reduce secondary infections, including medication adherence, vaccination (57 references). The second group emphasized lifestyle factors, such as diet, stress reduction, and hygiene practices (43 references).

Conclusions: Researchers could expand on this literature by creating specific prevention programs that integrate medical approaches to prevent infections. Furthermore, research could investigate the impact of early preventive care and customized health education on reducing secondary infections and enhancing quality of life in adolescents with gastrointestinal disorders.

Keyword 1: Gastrointestinal disorders

Keyword 2: Prevention

Keyword 3: Infections

Keyword 4: Adolescents

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2. **I confirm that the abstract constitutes consent to publication:** Yes
3. **I confirm that I submit this abstract on behalf of all authors:** Yes